

*HIGH VELOCITY TEARING TESTS ON FIBER-PLASTIC COMPOSITES
USING THE "STADIUM SPECIMEN"*

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ABSTRACT

Calculations on the impact behaviour of fiber-plastic composites (FPC) start from the assumption that stiffness as well as strength of 0°-laminates are independent of the high velocities of deformation that are generated during impact.

In order to find a proof for the assumption mentioned, i.e. that material characteristics of 0°-laminates are independent of time, high velocity tearing tests (10^3 to 10^7 %/h) were carried out by the Institut für Kunststoffverarbeitung (IKV). The experiments were designed to examine the material behaviour at impact stress. In the experiment, a pronounced force has to be introduced into the test specimen within a very short period of time (2 ms). The recently developed "Stadium Specimen" fits this purpose, since, unlike conventional quadrangular specimens, which involve force introduction by frictional resistance, force introduction is positive.

The paper will present the profits provided by this new type of test specimen, making a comparison to conventional quadrangular specimens. With increasing strain rates, stiffness and strength, both being subject to the actual type of fiber, also increase. This must be taken into consideration during calculation of fiber-plastic composites' impact behaviour.

KEYWORDS: Composites; high velocity tearing test; loading, impact; test specimen; viscoelastic

1. INTRODUCTION

Fibre-plastic composites (FPC) offer excellent properties, i.e. lightweight, high specific strength and stiffness. As a result the applications of these new materials increase, especially at the outside of cars, airplanes and machines, where the composites are subject to impact by falling stones or tools.

Calculations on the impact behaviour of FPC start from the assumption that material characteristics of 0° -laminates are independent of the deformation rate, which occurs during the impact /1/. So, normally material data, which are important for the calculation, are determined in short-term tensile tests with low strain rates.

New investigations at the Institut für Kunststoffverarbeitung (IKV) in Aachen aim at proofing this assumption in high velocity tearing tests. High velocity tearing tests allow the determination of stress/strain diagrams in a range of strain rates between 10^3 and 10^7 %/h. Before carrying out these tests, a new test specimen had to be developed, i.e. the "Stadium Specimen".

2. THE "STADIUM SPECIMEN"

In the high-velocity tearing test on 0° -laminates, pronounced force up to 3000 MPa has to be introduced into the test-specimen within a very short period of time (2 ms). When using conventional quadrangular specimens, stable and heavy jaws are the consequence. But heavy jaws cannot be used for high-velocity tearing tests, since this would cause a decrease of the natural vibrations in the spring-mass system load cell-jaw. As a result falsifying amplitude fluctuations of the force signal would be measured by the piezoelectric load cell.

These requirements to a new test specimen lead to the development of the "Stadium-Specimen". This name was chosen, since the specimen has the form of a soccer stadium

(figure 1).

FIGURE 1: Mount of the "stadium-specimen"

Compared to the quadrangular specimen, this new type of specimen has the following advantages:

- the testing force is introduced positively and not by friction as is the case with the quadrangular specimen
- despite of the pronounced force, which has to be introduced into the specimen, the weight of the jaws is only 500g and causes a neglectable decrease in natural vibrations
- the stadium specimen can be manufactured and reproduced very easily by using the winding process and a special core (see chapter 3)
- unlike the quadrangular specimen, no notch effect exists at the transition from the jaw to the specimen right above the jaw.

3. MANUFACTURING OF THE "STADIUM SPECIMEN"

The Stadium Specimen is produced in the winding process. A special winding core was designed, which enables the production of 10 specimens in one process (figure 2).

FIGURE 2: Winding core for the Stadium-Specimen

After winding, the specimens are cured on the core in an autoclave. The winding core consists of many plates, so that it is very easy to remove the specimens by disassembling the core.

4. TEST MATERIALS

The tests were carried out on specimens, made of glass (GRP), aramid (ARP) or carbon fibre reinforced epoxy-resin (CRP). The specimens were cured for two hours in an autoclave at a pressure of 7 bar and a temperature of 125 °C.

5. COMPARISON OF THE STADIUM SPECIMEN WITH THE CONVENTIONAL QUADRANGULAR SPECIMEN IN THE SHORT-TERM TENSILE TEST

To show the applicability of the Stadium Specimen, tensile tests were carried out with the conventional quadrangular and the Stadium Specimen. For short-term tensile tests, heavy jaws can be used for the fact that, as a result of the low strain rates during the tensile test, the weight of the jaws has no influence on the measured force signal. For the comparison the same fibres and resins were used for the two specimens. The tensile tests were carried out in a strain-controlled way as to reduce the measurement scatterings.

The strain was measured by resistance strain gauge. Figure 3 shows the comparison between the stress/strain-diagrams of the two specimens at identical strain rates and testing temperatures for the example of a carbon fibre reinforced laminate.

FIGURE 3: Stress-strain diagram: quadrangular - Stadium Specimen

The same results can be measured with glass and aramid fibres. From the results, it can be concluded that the same characteristic values, i.e. Young's modulus, tensile strength, failure strain, etc. can be measured on the stadium and the quadrangular specimen.

6. HIGH VELOCITY TEARING TESTS WITH THE STADIUM SPECIMEN

For the high velocity tearing test, a hydraulic testing machine was available with a maximum testing force of 50 KN and a piston velocity of 8 m/s. The specimen strain was measured by a very fast optical system, consisting of two cameras. For that purpose, the specimens were prepared with two measuring marks with a distance of 50 mm.

The Stadium Specimens, made of carbon, aramid and glassfibres were tested at room temperature in a strain rate range from 10^3 %/h to 10^7 %/h. The influence of the strain rate on the stress/strain behaviour of the laminates reinforced with carbon fibre is shown in figure 4.

FIGURE 4: Stress-strain diagram for CRP

7. EVALUATION OF THE HIGH VELOCITY TEARING TESTS

The stress/strain diagrams gained in high velocity tearing tests were approximated by a formula, which was developed for short term tensile tests /2/ :

$$\sigma = \epsilon E_0 (1 - D_1 \epsilon)$$

By the approximation, E_0 and D_1 are determined, with E_0 being the value for the Young's modulus and D_1 describing the bending of the stress/strain curve. When $D_1 = 0$, the material behaviour is linear elastic (Hookian law). In figure 5, these two characteristic material data E_0 and D_1 are shown for the carbon fibre reinforced laminate as a function of the strain rate.

As the strain rate increases the elastic modulus of the carbon-fibre reinforced laminate increases by 40 %, and D_1 remains constant at -4, which means that the stress/strain curve is progressive.

FIGURE 5: Mastercurve for the 0°-CRP composite

One of the major reasons is that the fibre waviness decreases. The increasing stiffness of the laminates corresponds with an increase in failure stress σ_B , whereas no influence on the failure strain ϵ_B could be found.

In the aramid fibre reinforced laminate, only a slight influence of the strain rate on the stiffness is determined. While the failure stress is independent of the strain rate, the failure strain decreases as the strain rate increases, which indicates increasing brittleness.

The glass fibre reinforced laminate shows also a dependance on the strain rate. The Young's modulus increases by 20 % in a range of strain rates between 10^3 and 10^7 %/h. The same effect was found for the tensile strength and the failure strain.

8. CONCLUSIONS

The success of fibre-plastic composites steeply depends on a comprehensive and complete description of the material behaviours. Especially, important designing data, like Young's modulus and tensile strength must, as was shown in this lecture, be described in characteristic value functions in dependance of the strain rate and in this form become available for the designer. Thus, the excellent properties of the composites can be used in a better way, instead of using "reduction factors" for considering the time influence on the material behaviour. Further investigations are planned at the IKV, so as to determine the time dependent material behaviour of 90° -laminates by high velocity tearing tests. In addition, a material model will be developed, so as to predict the damages which occur during an impact, with the help of Finite Element Analysis Method and time dependent characteristic value functions.

9. REFERENCES

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